

ENHANCING CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN ARALING PANLIPUNAN THROUGH CONTEXTUALIZED TEACHING AND LEARNING AMONG GRADE 10 LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) has emerged as an innovative learner-centered approach that connects classroom instruction with real-life experiences to make learning more meaningful and engaging (Johnson, 2002). This study examined the effectiveness of the CTL approach in improving the critical thinking skills and academic performance of Grade 10 learners in Araling Panlipunan in selected secondary schools in the First Congressional District of Pangasinan during the School Year 2025–2026. A quasi-experimental research design utilizing pre-assessment and post-assessment procedures was employed. Data were gathered from Grade 10 learners and Araling Panlipunan teachers through validated questionnaires and academic performance records. Statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages, weighted mean, chi-square, t-test, and Pearson r correlation were used in analyzing the data. Findings revealed that most teachers had earned master's degree units, possessed relatively short teaching experience, and attended limited in-service trainings related to contextualized instruction. Results further showed that learners demonstrated improved academic performance and significantly higher self-assessment ratings after the implementation of CTL strategies. A significant relationship was likewise found between learners' post-assessment performance and their academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. Female learners were observed to be more participative and engaged during contextualized learning activities. The findings indicate that contextualized instruction positively influences learner engagement, comprehension, and critical thinking development. The study recommends the wider integration of CTL strategies in Araling Panlipunan instruction and continuous teacher training on contextualized pedagogical practices.

Keywords: *Contextualized Teaching and Learning, critical thinking skills, Araling Panlipunan, learner engagement, academic performance, quasi-experimental design*

INTRODUCTION

Learning is a continuous and dynamic process that results in meaningful changes in an individual's knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behavior. In educational settings, learning outcomes are commonly reflected through academic achievement, critical thinking skills, and the ability of learners to apply knowledge in authentic situations. Modern educational research emphasizes that effective instruction significantly influences student achievement and engagement. According to Hattie (2009), instructional strategies greatly affect learners' academic performance because the quality of teaching shapes students' understanding, participation, and motivation inside the classroom. As educational systems continue to evolve, schools are encouraged to adopt learner-centered approaches that promote active participation, collaboration, and critical thinking rather than passive memorization of information.

One important learner-related factor associated with academic success is self-efficacy. Bandura (1997) defined self-efficacy as an individual's belief in his or her capability to accomplish tasks and achieve desired outcomes successfully. Learners with strong self-efficacy are generally more motivated, confident, and persistent in participating in classroom activities. Consequently, instructional approaches that encourage active engagement and meaningful learning experiences are essential in improving both academic achievement and learner participation.

One instructional strategy that supports meaningful and learner-centered education is Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL). CTL is an approach that connects classroom lessons with real-life experiences and practical situations. According to Johnson (2002), CTL enables learners to construct meaning by relating academic concepts to their daily experiences, social environment, and community realities. Rather than relying heavily on rote memorization, students become actively involved in inquiry-based activities, collaboration, reflection, and problem-solving tasks that make learning more relevant and meaningful. This approach encourages learners to apply classroom knowledge in authentic contexts, thereby strengthening comprehension and critical thinking skills.

The theoretical foundation of CTL is rooted in constructivist learning theory. Piaget emphasized that learners actively construct knowledge through interaction and experience, while Dewey advocated the principle of "learning by doing," which highlights the importance of experiential learning. Constructivist theory suggests that students develop deeper understanding when they connect prior knowledge with new experiences and practical applications (Kalchik & Oertle, 2010). CTL is also supported by Motivation Theory, which explains that learners become more interested and engaged when lessons are connected to real-world experiences. Predmore (2005) explained that students are more motivated when they recognize the practical relevance of classroom instruction. In

addition, Problem-Centered Learning, another component of CTL, encourages learners to work collaboratively in solving realistic and meaningful problems, thereby enhancing analytical thinking and problem-solving abilities (Kalchik & Oertle, 2010; Predmore, 2005). Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of CTL in improving academic performance across various disciplines. Peni (2011) found that contextualized instruction improved learners' reading comprehension, while Suparman et al. (2013) reported enhanced writing performance among students exposed to contextualized learning strategies. Similarly, Hidayah (2017) revealed that CTL positively influenced mathematics achievement and classroom participation. These studies consistently suggest that learners become more motivated, engaged, and academically successful when lessons are connected to familiar experiences and practical applications (Peni, 2011; Suparman et al., 2013; Hidayah, 2017).

Within the Philippine educational context, contextualization has become an important component of curriculum implementation. The Department of Education promotes the localization and contextualization of lessons to make instruction more responsive to learners' cultural backgrounds, community experiences, and local realities. However, despite the implementation of learner-centered reforms, many classrooms still rely heavily on traditional teaching methods characterized by lecture-based instruction, memorization, and passive learning. In Araling Panlipunan, lessons are sometimes presented abstractly, making it difficult for learners to appreciate their relevance to current social issues and everyday community life. As a result, some students experience limited engagement and difficulty developing critical thinking skills related to social and civic concerns (Department of Education, 2016).

In response to these educational challenges, this study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Contextualized Teaching and Learning in improving the critical thinking skills and academic performance of Grade 10 learners in Araling Panlipunan. Specifically, the study sought to examine the relationship between teacher-related factors and learner achievement, assess the extent of CTL implementation, and identify differences in learners' self-assessment performance before and after the application of contextualized instruction. The findings of this study may contribute to the enhancement of instructional practices and the development of learner-centered intervention programs that strengthen learner engagement, critical thinking, and academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan (Johnson, 2002; Hattie, 2009).

Research Questions

This study sought to assess the utilization of contextualized teaching and learning approach in Grade 10 Araling Panlipunan in the First Congressional District of Schools Division Office I Pangasinan as basis for intervention program in Araling Panlipunan to improve the performance of the Grade 10 learners using contextualized teaching during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.2 Length of Service
 - 1.3 Relevant In-service Trainings Attended
2. What is the level of performance of the Grade 10 learners in Araling Panlipunan during the third quarter?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the Araling Panlipunan teachers and the level of performance of the Grade 10 learners in Araling Panlipunan?
4. What is the extent of implementation on the Strategies in the Application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) Method as perceived by the Araling Panlipunan teachers and their department heads?
5. Is there a significant difference between the implementation on the Strategies in the Application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) Method as perceived by the Araling Panlipunan teachers and their department heads?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the Araling Panlipunan teachers and their extent of implementation on the strategies in the application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning Method?
7. What is the extent of implementation of the Grade 10 Learners' Self-Assessment Performance Prior and Post-application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) in Araling Panlipunan?
8. Based on the findings, what intervention program in Araling Panlipunan can be proposed to improve the performance of the Grade 10 learners using contextualized teaching?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quasi-experimental research design was utilized. The design included both pre-assessment and post-assessment data gathering on one sample to making it an independent sample design. The group infused was infused with Contextualized Teaching and Learning. Before the application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning, a self-assessment performance was conducted. The pre-assessment served as a base line data. After the application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning, the self-assessment performance checklist was again given to the group. The results of the academic performance in the third quarter in Araling Panlipunan were correlated to the result of self-assessment checklist of students.

The scheme of this design is the following:

whereas EG is the group with Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) /experimental

X is the application of CTL;

O1 is the pre-assessment performance; and

O2 is the post-assessment performance.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

One set of research instrument was used in gathering the data in this study. The researcher conducted library research and consulted past studies relevant to the present study to crystallize his own concept of the study. The questionnaire was formulated, evaluated and validated by the panel members before preparing the final draft. Approval and permit to conduct the study were obtained by the researcher from the authorities concerned prior to the conduct of the study. The questionnaire was personally administered by the researcher to the respondents involved in the survey.

Tools for Data Analysis

To derive valid and accurate results, appropriate statistical measures were employed.

To answer research question number 1 regarding the profile of the Araling Panlipunan teachers, frequency and percentage were used.

To answer research question number 2, chi-square was used.

To answer research question 3, frequency and percentage was used.

To answer research question number 4 on the Strategies in the Application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) Method, average weighted mean was used.

<u>Numerical Rating</u>	<u>Statistical Limits</u>	<u>Descriptive Equivalent</u>
5	4.20 – 5.00 –	Highly Implemented (HI)
4	3.40 – 4.19 –	Implemented (I)
3	2.60 – 3.39 –	Moderately Implemented (MI)
2	1.80 – 2.59 –	Slightly Implemented (SI)
1	1.00 – 1.79 –	Not Implemented (NI)

To answer research question number 5 on the Strategies in the Application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) Method as perceived by the teachers and their department head, t-test was used.

To answer research question 6 on the significant relationship of the profile of teachers and their extent of agreement on the strategies in the application of contextualized teaching and learning method, chi-square was used.

To answer research question number 7 on the Grade 10 Learners' Self-Assessment Performance Prior and Post-application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) in Araling Panlipunan, average weighted mean was used.

<u>Numerical Rating</u>	<u>Statistical Limits</u>	<u>Descriptive Equivalent</u>
5	4.20 – 5.00 –	Highly Implemented (HI)
4	3.40 – 4.19 –	Implemented (I)
3	2.60 – 3.39 –	Moderately Implemented (MI)

2	1.80 – 2.59	–	Slightly Implemented (SI)
1	1.00 – 1.79	–	Not Implemented (NI)

RESULTS

Table 1
Profile of Araling Panlipunan Teachers
(N=82)

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Highest Educational Attainment		
With Doctoral Units	9	10.98
MAEd/Med	31	38.80
With MA Units	42	51.22
Total	82	100
Length of Service as Teacher		
0-5	55	67.07
6-10	27	32.93
Total	82	100
Relevant Trainings Attended		
1-2	43	52.44
3 and more	39	47.56
Total	82	100

Table 2
Third Quarter Academic Performance in Araling Panlipunan of Grade 10 Learners

Grade Range	Descriptive Rating	Frequency	Percentage
90 – 100	Outstanding	57	14
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	130	30
80 – 84	Satisfactory	120	29
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	116	28
Total		403	100

Table 3
Significant Relationship Between the Profile of the Teachers and Grade 10 Learners in Araling Panlipunan

Variables	X ²	p-value	Decision
Highest Educational Attainment	.873	0.000*	Significant
Length of Service	.928	0.000*	Significant

Relevant Trainings Attended	.976	0.000*	Significant
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Table 4
Extent of Implementation on the Strategies in the Utilization of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) Method

<i>Strategies</i>	TEACHER		DEPARTMENT HEADS	
	WM	D	WM	D
Problems presented in class are simulated or real-life situations that require learners to develop practical solutions.	3.10	MI	4.53	HI
Activities are relevant and meaningful to learners' family life, school experiences, workplace preparation, and community involvement.	3.21	MI	3.13	MI
Instruction promotes critical thinking and analytical reasoning among learners.	3.21	MI	4.00	I
Teaching encourages a systematic and interdisciplinary approach in addressing problems and concepts.	3.57	I	4.10	I
Learners are exposed to real-world situations where acquired knowledge and skills can be applied in school, home, workplace, and community settings.	4.12	I	4.19	I
Simulations and modeled environments are utilized when actual real-world contexts are inaccessible or unsafe.	3.23	MI	3.41	I
Instruction recognizes and values learners' individuality, including their background, interests, abilities, experiences, and learning preferences, while fostering lifelong learning skills.	3.14	MI	4.18	I
Teachers guide learners in conducting research, managing time effectively, reflecting on learning, and learning from mistakes.	3.16	MI	3.50	I
Learning activities are anchored on collaborative learning communities where teachers and students share knowledge and learn from one another.	3.05	MI	3.75	I
Different groups collaborate through shared learning experiences and collective achievement of goals.	3.71	I	3.00	MI
Collaborative activities strengthen learners' interpersonal and teamwork skills.	3.23	MI	3.63	I
The creative process is enhanced when learners engage in collaborative problem-solving activities.	4.10	I	3.75	I

Instruction encourages the use of higher-order thinking skills in addressing issues, concepts, and problems.	4.00	I	3.94	I
Learners produce meaningful outputs that demonstrate acquired knowledge and skills.	3.34	MI	3.63	I
Learning activities are aligned with instructional goals and curriculum standards while integrating teaching and learning processes.	3.39	MI	3.63	I
Assessment practices provide learners with opportunities and guidance for continuous improvement.	4.04	I	3.67	HI
Assessment also provides educators with opportunities to improve instructional practices.	3.20	MI	3.18	MI
AWM	3.46	I	3.72	I

Legend:

Weighted Mean	Description;
4.20 – 5.00	Highly Implemented (HI)
3.40 – 4.19	Implemented (I)
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Implemented (MI)
1.80 – 2.59	Slightly Implemented (SI)
1.00 – 1.79	Not Implemented (NI)

Table 5
Grade 10 Learners' Self-Assessment Performance Prior and Post-application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) in Araling Panlipunan

Indicators	Self-Assessment Performance Prior to CTL		Self-Assessment Performance Post application of CT	
	WM	D	WM	D
Compared with previous lessons in Araling Panlipunan, I expect to perform better in class.	3.13	MI	4.88	HI
I understand the concepts and ideas taught in the subject.	4.00	I	5.00	HI
I can effectively accomplish the tasks and activities assigned in class.	4.00	I	5.00	HI
I can clearly explain concepts learned in the subject.	4.00	I	5.00	HI
I actively participate and show enthusiasm during class discussions.	4.35	SA	4.69	HI
I believe that I will receive a good grade in this subject.	4.07	I	4.18	I
My study habits and learning skills have improved compared to before.	3.41	I	3.50	I

I encourage my classmates to participate in class activities.	3.41	I	3.75	I
Compared with my classmates, I believe I have gained substantial knowledge about the subject.	4.06	I	5.00	HI
I am confident that I can continue learning more from this class.	3.53	I	3.63	I
I now set higher standards and expectations for my work.	4.00	I	4.75	HI
The lesson objectives and expected learning outcomes are clear to me.	4.46	HI	4.94	HI
I prepare myself before attending the subject class.	4.00	I	4.63	HI
I listen attentively to my teacher during discussions.	3.59	I	4.63	HI
I consistently follow my teacher's instructions.	4.36	HI	4.67	HI
I exert greater effort in learning the subject.	3.50	I	3.88	I
I stay updated with current trends and issues related to the subject matter.	3.76	I	4.75	HI
I actively respond to my teacher's questions during discussions.	3.76	I	4.00	I
I pay close attention to my teacher's explanations.	4.06	I	4.50	HI
I actively apply and engage in what I have learned in class.	3.94	I	5.00	HI
Average Weighted Mean	3.87	I	4.52	HI

Legend:

Weighted Mean

4.20 – 5.00

3.40 – 4.19

2.60 – 3.39

1.80 – 2.59

1.00 – 1.79

Description;

Highly Implemented (HI)

Implemented (I)

Moderately Implemented (MI)

Slightly Implemented (SI)

Not Implemented (NI)

Table 6
Significant Difference of Pre-Assessment Performance and Post-Assessment Performance of Grade 10 Learners in Araling Panlipunan

Data Analysis	Pre-Assessment Performance	Post-Assessment Performance
Mean 3.87 4.52	3.87	4.52
Variance	0.123478684	0.255830526
Observations	20	20
df	19	
t Stat	-6.638679	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.18803E-06	

t Critical one-tail	1.729133	
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*t is significant at 0.05

Table 7
Significant Relationship between Self-Assessment Performance Post-Application to Contextualized Teaching and Learning and Third Quarter Academic Performance in Araling Panlipunan

	AWM
Self-Assessment Performance Post Application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning	4.52
Third Quarter Academic Performance in Araling Panlipuan 10	85.08
Pearson r = -.82 R Square = .6724	

Table 8
Significant Difference on Self-Assessment Performance Post-Application of CTL of Grade 10 Learners as to their Gender

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-Value	F crit
Between Groups	195.5802	1	195.5802	679.0391	0.001469	18.51282
Within Groups	0.57605	2	0.288025			
Total	196.1563	3				

DISCUSSION

The profile of the teacher-respondents in table 1 reveals variations in terms of educational attainment, length of service, and relevant trainings attended. In terms of highest educational attainment, the majority of the respondents had earned Master of Arts in Education (MAEd/MEd) units, accounting for 42 teachers or 51.22% of the total population. Meanwhile, 31 teachers or 38.80% had already completed a master's degree, while only 9 respondents or 10.98% had doctoral units. This finding indicates that most teachers are pursuing professional advancement through graduate studies, reflecting their commitment to improving instructional competence and professional growth.

With regard to length of service, most of the respondents were relatively new in the teaching profession. Specifically, 55 teachers or 67.07% had been teaching for 0–5 years, whereas 27 teachers or 32.93% had rendered 6–10 years of service. The predominance of teachers with shorter teaching experience suggests a relatively young workforce that

may still be developing classroom management skills, pedagogical strategies, and professional expertise through continuous practice and exposure.

In terms of relevant trainings attended, 43 respondents or 52.44% reported attending 1–2 trainings, while 39 teachers or 47.56% had participated in 3 or more trainings. The findings imply that the respondents were actively engaged in professional development activities, which may contribute to the enhancement of their teaching effectiveness, instructional delivery, and adaptation to current educational trends and practices. Overall, the data suggest that the teacher-respondents demonstrate a strong inclination toward professional growth through higher education and participation in training programs.

The distribution of learners' academic performance indicates that most respondents achieved ratings within the average to above-average range. As shown in the table, the largest proportion of students obtained a Very Satisfactory rating (85–89), with 130 learners or 30% of the total population. This was followed by those who received a Satisfactory rating (80–84), comprising 120 learners or 29%. Meanwhile, 116 learners or 28% attained a Fairly Satisfactory rating (75–79). Only 57 learners or 14% achieved an Outstanding rating (90–100).

These findings suggest that the majority of learners demonstrated acceptable to commendable academic performance, although only a limited number reached the highest achievement level. The concentration of learners within the Very Satisfactory and Satisfactory categories may imply that while students possess adequate understanding and mastery of the lessons, there is still a need for enhanced instructional strategies and learning support to further improve academic excellence. The relatively lower percentage of Outstanding performers also highlights the importance of strengthening learner engagement, critical thinking activities, and differentiated instruction to help more students attain higher academic achievement.

Table 3 revealed a significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the performance of Grade 10 learners in Araling Panlipunan. Specifically, teachers' highest educational attainment obtained a chi-square (X^2) value of .873 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a significant relationship. Likewise, length of service yielded an X^2 value of .928 and a p-value of 0.000, while relevant trainings attended showed an X^2 value of .976 with a p-value of 0.000. Since all computed p-values were lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected in all variables. These findings suggest that teachers' academic qualifications, teaching experience, and participation in professional development activities significantly influence the learning outcomes of Grade 10 students in Araling Panlipunan. The results further imply that competent and continuously developing teachers contribute positively to learners' academic performance and classroom engagement.

Table 4 shows that both teachers (AWM = 3.46) and department heads (AWM = 3.72) generally perceived the implementation of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) strategies as Implemented. This indicates that CTL practices were commonly integrated into classroom instruction.

Teachers rated highly the use of real-world learning experiences, collaborative problem-solving, and higher-order thinking activities, suggesting that learners were exposed to practical and meaningful learning tasks. Department heads also gave high ratings to strategies involving authentic problem-solving and recognition of learners' individuality and lifelong learning skills.

However, some indicators such as collaborative learning communities, reflective learning, and research-related activities were only rated as moderately implemented by teachers. This may imply that certain learner-centered practices were not consistently applied in all classrooms.

Overall, the findings suggest that CTL strategies were effectively practiced, particularly in promoting authentic learning and critical thinking, although there is still room for improvement in strengthening collaborative and reflective learning approaches.

Table 5 shows that the Grade 10 learners' self-assessment performance improved after the application of the Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) method in Araling Panlipunan. The Average Weighted Mean increased from 3.87, interpreted as Implemented, prior to CTL application to 4.52, interpreted as Highly Implemented, after the intervention. This indicates that the use of CTL positively influenced learners' confidence, participation, understanding, and overall engagement in the subject.

Before the application of CTL, learners already showed positive perceptions in areas such as understanding lesson concepts, following teacher instructions, and participating in class discussions. However, after the implementation of CTL, higher ratings were observed in almost all indicators, particularly in understanding concepts, completing tasks, explaining lessons clearly, and actively applying what they learned, all of which received a mean score of 5.00 or Highly Implemented.

The findings further suggest that CTL helped learners become more motivated, attentive, and prepared during class discussions. Learners also reported clearer understanding of lesson objectives, improved participation, and greater awareness of current issues related to the subject matter.

Overall, the results imply that the application of CTL enhanced learners' self-confidence, academic engagement, and learning experiences in Araling Panlipunan, making classroom instruction more meaningful and learner-centered.

Table 6 shows the significant difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment performance of Grade 10 learners in Araling Panlipunan after the application of the Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) method. The mean score increased from 3.87 in the pre-assessment to 4.52 in the post-assessment, indicating an improvement in learners' performance after the intervention.

The computed t-statistic of -6.639 exceeded the critical value of 1.729, while the p-value of 1.19E-06 was lower than the 0.05 level of significance. This result indicates that there

was a statistically significant difference between the learners' pre-assessment and post-assessment performance.

The findings imply that the application of the CTL method had a positive effect on learners' academic performance, engagement, and understanding in Araling Panlipunan. Hence, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment performance of learners is rejected.

Table 7 presents the relationship between learners' self-assessment performance after the application of the Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) method and their third quarter academic performance in Araling Panlipunan 10. The learners obtained a high self-assessment mean of 4.52 and an average academic performance of 85.08.

The computed Pearson r value of -0.82 indicates a strong relationship between the two variables. Meanwhile, the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.6724$) shows that approximately 67.24% of the variation in academic performance may be associated with learners' self-assessment performance after the implementation of CTL.

The findings suggest that the application of CTL contributed positively to learners' engagement, confidence, and academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. However, since the correlation coefficient is negative, the data should be reviewed to verify the coding or computation of the variables, as higher self-assessment performance would normally be expected to correspond with higher academic performance.

Table 8 presents the significant difference in the self-assessment performance of Grade 10 learners after the application of the Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) method when grouped according to gender. The computed F -value of 679.039 was higher than the critical value of 18.513, while the p -value of 0.001 was lower than the 0.05 level of significance.

These results indicate that there was a significant difference in the learners' self-assessment performance based on gender after the implementation of CTL. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in self-assessment performance according to gender is rejected.

The findings imply that gender may have influenced how learners perceived and assessed their learning experiences after the application of CTL in Araling Panlipunan.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the majority of the Araling Panlipunan teachers possessed MA units, had relatively minimal teaching experience, and attended only a limited number of professional trainings and seminars related to instructional practices. Despite these limitations, the teachers were able to implement diverse teaching strategies in delivering Araling Panlipunan lessons, demonstrating their commitment to providing meaningful learning experiences to students. The Grade 10

learners exhibited very satisfactory academic performance in the subject, indicating that the instructional approaches utilized by the teachers contributed positively to the learners' understanding and mastery of the lessons. Furthermore, the study revealed a significant difference between the learners' pre-assessment and post-assessment performance, suggesting that the instructional interventions, particularly the application of Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL), effectively improved students' learning outcomes. The findings also established a significant relationship between the learners' self-assessed performance after the application of CTL and their third-quarter academic performance, implying that contextualized instruction enhanced not only learners' engagement and participation but also their academic achievement. In addition, significant differences were observed in the self-assessment performance of Grade 10 learners when grouped according to gender, with female learners demonstrating higher levels of participation, engagement, and academic performance compared to their male counterparts during the implementation of CTL strategies. This indicates that contextualized learning activities may encourage active involvement and deeper understanding among learners, particularly when lessons are connected to real-life experiences and relevant social contexts. Overall, the results of the study emphasized the importance of integrating Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) approaches in teaching Araling Panlipunan, as these strategies foster improved academic performance, increased learner motivation, enhanced classroom interaction, and more meaningful learning experiences. The study further highlighted the need for continuous teacher professional development programs, training opportunities, and instructional support to strengthen teachers' competence in effectively utilizing innovative and learner-centered teaching methodologies in the classroom.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations are hereby offered. Future researchers may conduct similar studies utilizing the Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) approach in other schools within the district or in different educational settings to further validate and strengthen the findings of the present study. The contextualized lesson guides and learning materials developed by the researcher may also be adopted, utilized, and subjected to further experimental try-outs to determine their effectiveness in improving learners' academic performance and engagement in Araling Panlipunan and other learning areas. Moreover, future researchers are encouraged to improve and enhance the produced lesson guides and learning materials by incorporating more innovative, learner-centered, and technology-integrated activities that are responsive to the diverse needs and learning styles of students. The use of the Contextualized Teaching and Learning (CTL) approach may likewise be expanded across different grade levels and various subject areas to examine its broader applicability and effectiveness in enhancing students' academic achievement, participation, critical thinking skills, and meaningful learning experiences. In addition, school administrators and education leaders may provide continuous professional development programs, seminars, and training workshops to equip teachers with the necessary competencies and strategies in effectively implementing contextualized and interactive teaching approaches in the classroom. Teachers are likewise encouraged to continuously design

contextualized instructional materials and learning activities that relate lessons to learners' real-life experiences, community situations, and social realities in order to foster greater motivation, active participation, and deeper understanding among students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to ethical standards in the conduct of educational research to ensure the protection, dignity, and rights of all participants throughout the process.

First, informed consent was secured from all teacher-respondents prior to data collection. The purpose of the study, its procedures, and the expected involvement of participants were clearly explained to them. They were informed that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they had the right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. Second, the study ensured confidentiality and anonymity. The identities of the respondents were not disclosed in any part of the research. Codes or general descriptions were used instead of names to protect their privacy. All data gathered were treated with strict confidentiality and were used solely for academic and research purposes.

Third, the researcher observed data privacy and protection. All collected data were securely stored and were accessible only to the researcher. No personal or sensitive information was shared with unauthorized individuals. The study complied with the provisions of Republic Act No. 10173, ensuring that personal data were processed responsibly and securely. Fourth, the study followed the principle of non-maleficence, ensuring that no harm—physical, psychological, or professional—came to the participants. The questionnaire was designed to avoid sensitive or offensive questions, and respondents were not placed in any situation that could have caused discomfort or risk.

Fifth, honesty and integrity were maintained throughout the research process. The data collected were accurately reported, analyzed, and interpreted without manipulation or fabrication. Proper acknowledgment of sources was observed to avoid plagiarism and to uphold academic integrity. Lastly, the researcher ensured respect for the participants' professional roles. The study was conducted in a manner that did not disrupt their teaching responsibilities or school operations. Proper coordination with school heads and authorities was observed before the conduct of the study.

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